

Performance of Grade 10 Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Students of Bugallon in Relation to Selected Variables

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the level of performance of Grade 10 TLE students in public secondary schools in the municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan in relation to selected variables during academic year 2025-2026. The descriptive-correlational research design with the use of the questionnaire was used. The respondents were 16 Grade 10 TLE teachers who rated the academic performance of 467 Grade 10 TLE Students from the four (4) secondary schools in the Municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan. Findings show that the level of adequacy of the facilities and equipment is less adequate in all areas. The level of performance of the TLE learners, generally failed to meet the desired level of performance in the two (2) areas of specialization in the first and second quarter. The proposed plan of action is designed and be adopted in other schools for wider implementation to improve the level of performance of Grade 10 TLE Learners.

Keywords: *Performance of Grade 10 TLE Students, facilities and equipment, Agriculture, Home Economics, Information Communication Technology, Industrial Arts, Knowledge, Skills, Understanding Appreciation.*

Chapter 1
THE PROBLEM

Rationale

The Revised K to 12 Curriculum of the Department of Education has the main goal of giving the Filipino learners particularly the junior high school with excellent and relevant education in order for them to be equipped with 21st century skills and job ready. The recipients of this curriculum will become competitors as they acquire the global competence in knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes. They will become well-rounded individuals who have self-confidence and know-how in the performance of their profession they have chosen.

Speaking of performance and competence that these young Filipinos manifest from their education under the K to 12 Curriculum they can use the specific skills they developed in looking for a job. Learning outcomes according to Human Resource Development (2024) are those things than an individual must demonstrate to be effective in a job, role, function, task or duty. They include job- relevant behavior (what a person says or does that results in good or poor performance), motivation (how a person feels about a job, organization or geographic location) and technical knowledge/skills (what person knows/demonstrates regarding facts, technologies, a profession, procedures, a job, an organization). They are identified through the study of jobs and roles.

Winterton (2015) defines performance and competence in the context of training and development initiatives. It is the incorporation of knowledge skills, and values with a holistic typology. This maybe functional and cognitive competence or behavioral competence and occupational competence.

The learners under the K to 12 program are expected to possess these diversified areas of performance and competence. These under the areas of Technology and Livelihood Education with Agri- Fishery Arts Animal Production as their specialization must acquire the learning competencies in different dimensions. One of them is the so-called entrepreneurial competencies. Here they could acquire certain set of characteristics called personal entrepreneurial competencies which is vigilance for opportunities. It means when entrepreneurs view an opportunity for business he is quick to take it. Edwards (2023). He also commits to work which means the ability to deliver his promise promptly because he values his reputation for dependability and will do everything not back out on commitment. Furthermore, they will learn to take risks, seeking, able to systematize their plans and monitor them, and above all have self-confidence. An entrepreneur shows confidence in his work, knows how to do his work at this best.

In the K to 12 Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) Agri-Fishery Arts specialized in animal production the learners are exposed in developing their personal entrepreneurial competencies. It is in this period of schooling that they will be able to recognize the potential customer market in animal production, recognize the potential customer market in animal production business by using various techniques, select and procure stock, breeds, strains for poultry raising, provide feed and implement feeding practices, bonding, maintaining proper flock management, measures and therapeutic measures, and apply them in accordance with the industry and farm production standards.

They can acquire and develop these excellent performances by means of their strategic

and hands on experiences with the initiative of their teachers as they manifest their motivation and interest in their field of specialization.

In the K to 12 TLE Grade 10 learners can acquire the skills in Home Economics essential in effective performance of the task assigned to them. The Grade 10 learners can acquire competencies in recognizing needed personal entrepreneurial competencies in different areas of home economics like cookery, bread and pastry, housekeeping and many more. The learners can also acquire the skills in planning and preparing for installation of the devices and systems of computer, networking devices in accordance with job requirement conduct testing on the installed computer system diagnose and configure system and network and able to test the system and network as needed and as a part of skills to the acquired in Home Economics.

While the Grade 10 Learners engaged in Home Economics, develop the knowledge and skills needed when they encounter some problems that need immediate attention of the TLE and teachers and school administrators. These problems can be categorized as teacher's problem, and parents or home problems. Both the teachers and learners experience inadequacy of instructional materials, facilities and equipment and even strategies of teaching for the teachers which impede the acquisition skills of the learners. As explained by Winterton (2023) performance is used to plan, guide, and develop behavior, the absence of these materials used in performance development it is very hard to achieve the high quality of knowledge and skills competency that provide balance between strength and developmental needs.

Another side of the problems that affect the acquisition of good performance and competencies fall under student's area. They sometimes lack exposure in Home Economics. These create crucial problems due to the lack of hands on exposure along the line of agri-fishery arts and animal production. Their interest and motivation are affected by the attitude and feeling of lukewarm in acquiring quality performance in Home Economics and parental intervention are also contributory to the problems of competency acquisition. The lack of support and encouragement of parents, their lack of knowledge of the importance of Home Economics in daily life affect negatively the interest of the learners in the said area of specialization. As suggested by Slusher (2021) career and technical education courses such as Home Economics should assist learners in acquiring the competencies needed to achieve employability. Therefore, this study seeks to identify the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners learning competencies deemed necessary for entry-level, employment of senior high school graduates in the area of Home Economics. This is the challenge faced by the researcher to determine the high and low level of acquiring knowledge and skills in the area of performance by the Grade 10 learners in Technology Livelihood Education K to 12 Curriculum Program.

Thailand Agricultural Sector Inc. (2018) exemplified the concept of performance as referring to functional areas to behavior dominated by the management strategy as a key organization resource that could be exploited to gain competitive advantage. It is the collective learning in the organization especially how to coordinate diverse crop production skills and integrate multiple streams of farming technologies. The core approach to competence is that it recognizes the complex interaction of people, farming skills and technologies that drives firm performance and address the importance of learning and path dependency in its agricultural evolution.

Castellano (2019) surmised that regardless of the profession excellent performance in one's professional work role is importance in the overall learning process. Therefore providing a curriculum in which learners can acquire technical skills is essential and should be initiated

during high schools. In view of this efforts have been made to reform the curriculum to include more rigorous industry standards, and higher academic standards and related general education knowledge.

Green (2020) said that to ensure learners' knowledge and skills they are provided with opportunities to acquire the needed skills to be competitive in the workforces offers them sets of course offering in which they can declare major and specialize in a specific area manifested by career cluster. This is to address the needs of increasing integration of standards from both academia and industry while encompassing curricular changes and tools for measuring assessment of the program.

Vietnam Farming Associations (2020) implemented curriculum standards into its program to ensure that learners in agricultural education would be competent in securing employment or succeeding in port secondary education. Seven total career pathways were created for the agricultural systems, crop variation, crop cycle system and scientific farming methods.

Atienza (2019) disclosed facts about processing and marketing of livestock product in Indonesia providing almost all meat and eggs and part of the wild domestic consumption. The government of Indonesia is keenly aware of the importance of the livestock sector as a supplier of animal protein for human consumption, raw materials for industry and food processing for Agriculture. It has the potential to generate employments, increase rural income and result in the productive use of land.

The animal and crop science industry in Indonesia encompasses over a thousand slaughterhouses which are divided into three categories based on species slaughtered. Thus they are slaughterhouses for large ruminants for pigs and for poultry. They are classified into three types by the daily slaughter capacities: Type A for more than 100 heads slaughtered per day; type B for 500 to 100 heads per day; and type C or D for 5 to 50 heads slaughter per day. The crops are yield for the feeds for the piggeries to sustain the livestock with continuous support of agricultural produce like corn, rice and other derivatives for the animals to consume.

Ferrer (2020) gave his insights on basics for raising backyards clusters in organic farming. They were as follows: Get Your Chicks Off to a Good Start Baby poultry cannot general enough heat to sustain themselves. That is the reason the mother he keeps the your under her wings. The process of getting chocks off to a good start is called brooding. The brooding period is roughly the first 3 to 4 weeks of a chick's life. By then, most breeds are fully feathered and can generate enough heat on their own to get by.

Quiroz (2019) Standard of Facilities, of Home Economic, Equipment, and Supplies adequate office facilities should be provided. They should be clean, attractive, and sufficiently spacious to provide comfortable workspace for each teachers and learners to teach and learners to learn to house and to store records, maps, form, and supplies. The arrangement of space should encourage teamwork, promote self-esteem, minimize distracting sights and sounds, and help each teacher or learner work efficiently. Classrooms should be designed to accommodate learners with disabilities.

According to Tan (2020) an assessment facilities and classroom equipment should have furniture of adequate quality, design, and size to meet the needs of current office technology. Such furniture should include, but not be limited to, desks, chairs, worktables, counters, storage cabinets, coat racks, bookshelves, and filing cabinets. The arrangement should specialized furniture. Practicum activities workstation furniture should incorporate design features to reduce

stress on eyes, wrists, and lower back.

Wachira (2019) the facility should be designed to maintain orderly control of the operation and reduce the vulnerability of the staff or facility to acts of abuse and violence learners access should be restricted to specified areas, and separated from staff work areas. Emergency exits should be adequate and clearly marked, evacuation diagrams should be prominently displayed throughout the facility, and evacuation drills should be performed periodically. Identification badges, key/magnetic entry cards, and/or metal detectors should be considered. Exterior lightning of the building and grounds and teachers/learners who may use the facility after dark. Automated assessment offices house many valuable pieces of equipment, such as cameras, video recorders, and computers. The value of data stored on such equipment often exceeds the cost of replacing it. The facility should be designed to incorporate security measures and system to guard against losses from theft, vandalism, terrorism, fire and natural disaster.

Forever (2019) an assessment office equipment and facilities for Home Economics should have office machines in quantities and capabilities sufficient to meet the needs of the office. In addition to computers (which are discussed in section 5), such equipment would include, but not be limited to, the following: Photocopy machines – useful features include speed, auto feed, collation, reduction and enlargement, automatic stapling, and two-sided copy capabilities. Scanning and micrographic equipment – by storing images of documents and records on microfilm or magnetic or optical media, it is possible to make better use of office space, speed the retrieval of stored information, and enhance security. Consult state or provincial law for relevant standards on imaging and to determine if images are accepted as an archival medium. Mailing machine – in addition to speeding mailing operations, postage meters help control postage expenses.

Farming equipment – this category of equipment has become less prominent in assessment field because most of the functions can now be performed on motorized farming systems. However, manual farming is still useful for completing short forms, preparing soil, or cultivating idle lands.

Mendoza (2020) shared his insights on how to maintain facilities and equipment in Home Economics. He said that adequate facilities and equipment's must be maintained and managed for learners used. They shall be encouraged to use them effectively to achieve the necessary knowledge and skills expected of them during the duration of the course. In case of failure to monitor the correct use and manage the teacher in charge should encourage the learner to participate in the maintenance and management as a part of their learning.

Viray (2019) investigated on the level of adequacy of facilities and equipment in Home Economics in Pangasinan National High School. Her findings were moderately adequate in bread and pastry and in housekeeping. There was insufficient training of teacher's in bread and pastry and in housekeeping. Teacher's lacked National competency training, and failed to maintain their facilities and equipment to have better performance of the learners.

Dela Cruz (2018) conducted an investigation of Profile of Home Economics Teacher in Public Secondary schools in Pangasinan I/ Division. Her findings are teachers have the basic educational qualification, young at age, failed to upgrade their qualifications by training NC training, and attended 2 to 3 trainings in 3 years period. She recommended that the Home Economic teachers should take up NC training related to the subjects handled, attend seminars trainings and take up graduate courses related to their specialization.

Ulanday (2019) as a requirement of his masteral program conducted a study on performance of Home Economic Learners Basis for a proposed action plan his findings were to identify specific tools and equipment was moderate; they were still using the common forms of cooking materials and facilities and lack trainings and skills. Generally their level of using the equipment was fair due to the lack of training and exposure in Home Economics.

Enriquez (2018) in her investigation on proper operation and maintenance of Home Economics tools, and equipment by the teachers found out that they had poor knowledge and skills in using upgraded state of tools and select tools and operate tools. They were poor in checking tools defects, conducting pre-operation check-up and use the equipment and facilities in live of the procedures in handling them.

Manuel (2019) in his study on Preventive Maintenance Practices of the Home Economics Teachers in the tools, materials and facilities, disclosed that the teachers were moderate in performing routine check-up and maintenance of tools and equipment in line with the procedures; moderate in lay outing plan of different types of activities in housekeeping, bread and pastry, and cookery, low in knowledge of provision of classrooms management principles and moderate in applying appropriate safety measures.

Carrera (2018) as a part of his graduate degree course conducted a study on skills of Learners in Home Economics in Private Secondary schools in Dagupan City. Her findings were: Home Economics learners were moderate in generating business idea that relates with career choice in Home Economic; preparing hand tools and equipment; and performing mensuration and calculations. They were low in identifying kinds of technical application of interpreting the skills learned and in evaluating hazards and risks in Home Economics Facilities. The overall findings where they were generally deficient competencies in the different areas of Home Economics Technology.

De Leon, (2020) conducted a study on food processing as a service of livelihood activities of the TLE learners of Pangasinan National High School. His findings were the learners' performance was highly affected by the lack of facilities and equipment, the educational qualification of the teacher affected moderate the performance of the teacher.

Thus, it is optimistic enough that the results of the study can contribute to the improvement of performance and competencies of Grade 10 TLE Learners in Home Economics particularly in the learning areas such as food processing.

Theoretical Framework

This study will be based from the theory of cognitive learning by Bruner (1981), as cited by Bautista (2024), elucidated the important aspects that indicates and indicative learning methodology of the teachers in delivering quality education to the learners. Which is divergent, direct, open and student centered. It means that the teaching of Home Economics, an area of specialization of the Grade 10 TLE learners should consider the learner as the center of learning and that he must be aided from the inductive principle of reasoning of his own understanding of the topics the studied. He is expected to develop the skills on concept formation, interpretation of data, application of principles for the learning of Home Economics.

Another theory of learning is the theory of constructivism by Powell and Kalina (1998), as cited by Calma (2021) in his study, this theory applies the principle of the law of exercise and practice, law of readiness and motivation, drills and exercise connect learning to past experiences. In the teaching of Grade 10 TLE focused on Home Economics constant practice, hands-on

activities on the different dimensions can result to mastery and therefore higher extent of implementation of the learning competencies and better performance of the learners.

It perceives learning and process and is concerned about individual differences. This theory will be used in this study through student's attainment of learning competencies in Grade 10 TLE in the area of Home Economics that they must study further, analyze and rationalize the different competencies, their concepts and implications to improve one's skills and attitude.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The casual paradigm will be adopted as the model of the study. The independent variables concerned with the professional profile of grade 10 TLE teachers in terms of age, teacher's qualification, teachers rank, and specialized training attended for the last 3 years, and levels of adequacy of school facilities and equipment in Grade 10 TLE Home Economics in the areas of a Cookery, and Bread and Pastry Production. The dependent variable consisted of the performance of Grade 10 TLE learners along the area of specialization cookery, and bread and pastry production. Action plan will be formulated based from the findings of the study.

PARADIGM OF THE STUDY

Statement of the Problem

This study will determine the level of performance of the Grade 10 Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Learners in Relation to selected variables during the school year 2025-2026. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers in term of
 - a. Age,
 - b. Teacher's Qualification,
 - c. Teacher's Rank, and
 - d. Specialized Training Attended for the last 3 years?
2. What is the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in Home Economics in terms of:
 - a. Cookery, and
 - b. Bread and Pastry Production?
3. Is there a significant correlation between the level of performance of the level 10 TLE learners across profile variable?
4. What is the level of adequacy of school facilities and equipment in Grade 10 TLE of the public secondary schools in the above selected area of Home Economics?
5. Is there significant correlation between the school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners?
6. What action plan can be proposed to improve the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in Home Economics?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant correlation between the profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in areas of specialization under Home Economics.
2. There is no significant correlation between the level of adequacy of school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in areas of specialization under Home Economics.

Scope and Delimitation

This study aims to determine the level of performance of the Grade 10 Technology and Livelihood Education Learners in Home Economics in Relation to Selected Variables this school year 2025-2026. The schools are: Bugallon National High School, Irene Rayos Ombac National High School, Bugallon Integrated School, and Polong National High School. Respondents consisted of the total enumeration of sixteen (16) Grade 10 teachers and total enumeration of four hundred and sixty-seven (467) Grade 10 TLE learners as subject of the study.

Significance of the Study

This study will be beneficial to the following people:

Curriculum Planners. The results could challenge them to come up with adequate instructional materials, facilities and equipment to implement better the learning competencies in Home Economics.

School Administrators. They will be able to design better programs of activities and projects and monitoring activities for better implantation of the learning competencies in Grade 10 TLE Home Economics.

TLE Teachers. The result/findings of the study will guide and give the TLE teachers clear picture of the status of the level of performance of learners in Grade 10 TLE in Home Economics. It could provide them the needed instructional materials and equipment/facilities to level up the implementation of the learning competencies.

TLE Student. They will be able to improve their learning competencies and performance with the proper use of strategies by their teachers, adequacy of the instructional materials, facilities, and equipment needed in Grade 10 TLE.

Parents. They could have an idea on what skills and competencies and level of performance being acquired and developed by their children and cooperate with the school for attaining better learning of Home Economics.

Researcher. He could improve his teaching and management of the classroom through the use of the proposed action plan. He could discover the flows of teaching TLE, his weakness and strategies and made better commitment for serving the learners.

Future Researchers. They could have an idea in how Grade 10 TLE specialization in Home Economics, are being implemented, the strengths and weakness so that they could conduct similar research to improve the findings of the present study.

Definition of Terms

The following terms will be defined operationally or lexically to shed light on the findings of this investigation.

Bread and Pastry Production. It is referred to as mix and bake ingredients according to recipes to produce small quantities of bread, pastries, and other baked goods for consumption on premise or for sale as specialty baked goods (<http://occupationalinfo.org>)

Cookery. In this study it refers to any operation that prepares food for consumption by the public which can be fast food in restaurant, dinner house or white table cloth restaurants (<https://www/commercialcooking.html>)

Home Economics. In this study it deals in the area of specialization in TLE 10 which the learners acquire skills, knowledge and competencies in the different corporate of Home Economics like pastry, cookery, and housekeeping.

Performance. It refers in this study, as the activities or ways on how the learning competencies of Grade 10 TLE learners specialized in Home Economics particularly on bread and pastry, cooking housekeeping, food and beverage, and food processing.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter present the research design, the procedures, the date gathering instruments used by the research and statistical tools used in the analysis and interpretation of data.

Research Design

This investigation will use the descriptive-correlated design. Descriptive according to Best (2007) it is used to establish the prevailing status of condition in particular areas of concern. Correlated Design is also suitable to situation which calls for analysis of relationship without variable manipulation. It can show the magnitude or degree of relationship between variables. Descriptive Correlational Design is used in a study which focuses in the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in relation to certain variables such as profile of the TLE teachers and the level of adequacy of the facilities and equipment.

Locale and Population

This study will be conducted among the Grade 10 TLE learners in public secondary schools in the municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan during the school year 2025-2026.

The table below shows the exact number of respondents from the four (4) public secondary schools with 16 teachers and 467 learners as subjects taken in complete enumeration during the school year 2025-2026 as subjects of the study.

Table I
Distribution of Respondent by School

School	No. of TLE 10 learners	No. of Grade 10 TLE teachers
1. Polong National High School	98	4
2. Bugallon Integrated School	167	3
3. Irene Rayos Ombac National High School	70	4
4. Bugallon National High School	132	5
TOTAL	467	16

Data Gathering Instruments

This study will use the questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument.

Part 1 consisted of the profile of the teacher in terms of age, teacher's qualification, teachers rank, and specialized training attended for the last three (3) years.

Part 2 consisted of adequacy of facilities and equipment in TLE 10 learners along Home Economics particularly in specialized areas such bread and pastry, cooking housekeeping, food and beverage, and food processing as adopted from the list of Technical Education Skills and Authority (TESDA) in Taguig, Metro Manila.

Part 3 Consisted of level of performance of Grade 10 TLE learners in Home Economic taken from the grading sheets of TLE teachers from the first to second quarters SY 2025-2026 utilizing the DepEd order No.8 s, 2015.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured permission first from the Schools Division I Superintendent of Pangasinan I to conduct the study and then to the school principals of the different public secondary schools in the Municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan.

After permission will be granted she will prepare copies of questionnaire for administration to all the schools with the help of her teacher friends teaching in those different schools. It will take her three (3) weeks to administer and retrieve the instruments due to the distance and availability of the respondents and to ensure 100 percent retrieval. As part of the date needed in the study, she will be borrowing the grading sheets of the TLE 10 teachers for the 1st to the 2nd quarter for their performance where criteria will be taken like: Written Work, Performance Tasks, and Quarterly Assessment.

Statistics Treatment of Data

The data gathered were treated as follows:

To answer problem number 1 on the profile of the Grade 10 TLE teacher's frequency count and percentages will be used.

To answer problem 2 on the level of performance of Grade 10 TLE learners the following will be used: Written work 20% Performance task 60%, and quarterly assessment 20%. The ratings will be added to make up the grade for every quarter then interpret with description below:

90% - 100%	Outstanding
85% - 89%	Very satisfactory
80% - 84%	Satisfactory
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
74% and below	Poor

To answer problem 3 on determining the significant correlation between the Profile of the TLE 10 teachers and the level of performance of the grade 10 TLE learners. Spearman Rank Correlation will be used with the aid of SPSS for computation.

To answer problem number 4 on the level of adequacy of the school facilities and equipment in TLE 10 of the public secondary schools in the municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan in Home Economics check mark will be used and then converted to percentage scales with their descriptive ratings as follows:

Percentage Scale	Descriptive Rating
75% and above	Highly Adequate
50% - 74%	Moderately Adequate
0% - 49%	Less Adequate

Problem 5 on determining the significant correlation between the level of adequacy of school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the TLE 10 learners SPEARMAN Rank Correlation Coefficient will be computed using the SPSS computer aided software.

Formula:

$$RS = 1 - \frac{6ED2}{N(N^2-1)}$$

Where:

$$1=K$$

$$6=K$$

ED2 = sum of the squares of the difference between two ranks

N = Number of pairs

For problem 6, to the proposed action plan it will be based form the findings of the study.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents analyses and interprets the data gathered in the light of problems draw in the study.

Profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers

Table 2 presents the profile of Grade 10 TLE Teachers of Home Economics in terms of age, Teacher's Qualification, Teacher's Rank, and specialized training attended for the last 3 years.

Table 2
Profile of the Teacher-Respondents Along age, Teacher's Qualification,
Teacher's Rank, specialized training attended.

Profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers		
A. Age	Frequency	Percentage
21 – 30	10	62.50%
31 – 40	4	25%
41 and above	2	12.80%
Total	16	100%

B. Teacher Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
MA/BSE with NC, TM and NTTC	4	12.50%
MA/BSE without TM and NTTC	12	75%
Total	16	100%

C. Teachers Rank	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher 1	13	81.13%
Teacher 2	1	16.25%
Teacher 3	1	16.25%
Master Teacher 1	1	16.25%
Master Teacher II	0	0%
Total	16	100%

D. Specialized Training in attended for the last 3 years	Frequency	Percentage
0 – 2 times	9	56.25%
3 – 4 times	5	31.25%
5 years and above	2	12.50%
Total	16	100%

The table shows the profile of the teachers in terms of age, educational qualification, teacher's rank, and specialized training attended in TLE for the last 3 years. There were 10 or 62.50 percent of the teachers who were under the age bracket of 21-30; 4 or 25 percent under 31-40; and 2 or 12.50 percent who were under the age bracket of 41 and above. It means that the teachers are strong and energetic to perform their duties and responsibilities. Along educational qualification, 12 or 75 percent of teachers with BSE without NC Training, 2 or 12.50 percent with MA degree; 2 or 12.50 percent with BSE, TM and NTTC no one of them has graduate or master degree. It means that the teachers have just the basic qualification to teach but failed to upgrade their educational qualification to improve their professional career. It implied that they failed to give importance of upgrading their educational perspective.

Regarding Teacher's rank; 13 or 81.13 percent were teachers 1; in 16.25 percent teachers 2; 1 or 16.25 percent were teacher 3; 1 or 16.25 percent were Master Teacher I; It means that the

teachers had not been promoted to higher rank. It implied that they were still young in service and their performance contributes to their chances for promotion to higher rank.

Performance of TLE 10 Learners in Home Economics Cookery (First Quarter)

Table 3 presents the performance of TLE 10 Learners in Home Economics Along Cookery in the first quarter.

Table 3
Performance of TLE 10 Learners Along Home Economics (First Quarter)
In Cookery

Schools	No. of Learners	Written Task 20%	Performance Task 60%	Quarterly Exams 20%	1 st Quarter Grade 100%	Level of Performance
1. Polong NHS	47	15.50	46.10	15.50	77.1	F
2. Bugallon Integrated School	34	16.70	47.15	16.10	79.95	S
3. Bugallon NHS	190	17.10	47.80	17.60	82.50	S
4. Iren Rayos Ombac NHS	150	17.50	46.40	16.72	80.62	S
Total Ave %	741	16.6	47.12	16.27	80.07	S

Data show that Bugallon National High School has fairly satisfactory level of performance. It means that the teachers failed to teach well the learners could not fully perform the tasks given them. The schools, Bugallon Integrated School, Polong National High School, Iren Rayos National High School, reveal satisfactory level of performance proven by their respective average ratings.

The findings mean that the learners have acquired certain knowledge and skills in Home Economics but failed to excel in the above average level. Implies that the teachers have taught the minimum level to develop that knowledge and skills of the learners in the dimension of Home Economics along cookery. It implies further that the learner's skill cannot perform independently the assigned activities to achieve positive results.

As a whole the level of performance of the 4 schools is satisfactory proven by the overall average percentage of 80.07percent. It only implies that the learners have not acquired the competencies fully as needed in performing the tasks and understanding in Cookery are still inadequate that could affect their written work, performance tasks, and their quarterly assessment.

Bread and Pastry

Table 4 presents the level of performance of TLE 10 Learners in Home Economics along Bread and Pastry in the second quarter.

Table 4
Level of Performance of TLE 10 Learners in Home Economics Along Bread and Pastry Production (Second Quarter)

Schools	No. of Learners	Written Works (20%)	Performance Task (60%)	Quality Assessment (20%)	2 nd Quarter Grade (100%)	Level of Performance
1. Polong NHS	47	15.65	46.45	15.80	77.7	Fair
2. Bugallon Integrated School	94	16.76	47.53	16.16	80.45	S
3. Bugallon NHS	115	16.85	47.90	16.84	81.55	S
4. Iren Rayos Ombac NHS	49	16.93	47.66	16.60	81.19	S
Overall Ave. %	741	16.85	47.38	16.51	80.74 (81)	S

It can be noticed that the following schools have obtained satisfactory level of performance in the second quarter in the four (4) public secondary schools. The findings mean that they have not fully acquired the knowledge, skills, and other competencies needed in the second quarter. It implied that their abilities do perform the work or the task needed in the second quarter are still insufficient. Bugallon National High School has fairly satisfactory performance.

As a whole, it could be deduced that the 4 schools recorded an overall average percentage of satisfactory proven by the overall average percentage of 80.7. It implied that these schools failed to perform higher as expected of them during the second quarter. This condition is due to the inadequate facilities and equipment needed to master the competencies in Home Economics along bread and pastry production.

Table 5 presents the summary of the level of performance of the TLE Grade 10 Learners along Home Economics.

Table 5
Summary of the Level of Performance of TLE 10 Learners
Along Home Economics

Schools	No. of Learners	First Quarter		Second Quarter	
		Grade	Performance Level	Grade	Performance Level
Bugallon NHS	132	75	Fair	78	Fair
Polong NHS	94	76.65	Fair	80.45	S
Bugallon Integrated School	115	74.14	Fair	82	S
Irene Rayos NHS	49	77.24	Fair	81.19	S
Overall Average Percentage %	457	77.46	Fair	81	S

It can be noted that the level of performance of Bugallon NHS in Home Economics is Fair during the first and second quarters, satisfactory in the third grading period, and very satisfactory in the fourth grading period. It means that their performance shows improvement per grading period. It implies that they are inspired to learn the necessary skills in Home Economics along the 2 areas.

Polong National High School has performance of fair in the 1st quarter satisfactory in the second quarter, very satisfactory in the third quarter, and very satisfactory in the fourth quarter. It means that Polong NHS has been successful in teaching the knowledge and skills in Home Economics. It implied that the teachers and the learners are on the process of promoting the importance of home economics in their everyday life.

Bugallon Integrated School has the same line of improvement in terms of performance with Polong NHS. In the first quartet it is fair, satisfactory in the second quarter, very satisfactory in the third quarter and outstanding in the fourth quarter. It means that their performance greatly improved every quarter.

Irene Rayos Ombac NHS has the same level of performance with Bugallon NHS which is fair in the first quarter, very satisfactory in the third quarter and outstanding in the fourth quarter.

As a whole the summary table revealed that the 4 schools have very satisfactory level of performance. It means that the schools have more or less moving toward a positive level of performance. It implied that the learners have acquired the needed knowledge, skills, and understanding of the competencies in Home Economics. It is reflected in their written works, performance tasks, and quarterly assessment.

Table 6 presents the correlation analysis between the profile of the grade 10 TLE teachers and the level of performance of the grade 10 TLE learners.

Table 6
Correlation on between the profile of the Grade 10 TLE Teachers and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE Learners.

Variables	R	P-Value	Decision
Profile of the Grade 10 TLE Teachers and the Level of Performance	.919	.041	Significant

The table shows that the profile of the Grade 10 TLE Teachers affects the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners. The computed P-value is .041 which is lower than the R computed value of 919. The result is significant therefore the null hypothesis is rejected “There is a significant correlation between the profile of the teachers and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners.”

Therefore, the profile of the Grade 10 TLE Teachers is significantly correlated with the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE Learners. It implied that the profile of the teachers affects the level of performance of the learners.

Home Economics Facilities and Equipment

Table 7 deals with level of adequacy of school facilities and equipment in Grade 10 TLE along Home Economics.

Table 7
Level of Adequacy of School Facilities and Equipment
along Home Economics

HOME ECONOMICS			
Facilities and equipment	Frequency	Percentage	DE
1. Mops	15	93.75	HA
2. Brushes	15	93.75	HA
3. Brooms	15	93.75	HA
4. Buckets	13	81.25	MA
5. Dust pans	14	87.80	MA
6. Garbage Plastic	13	81.25	MA
7. Sorting baskets	13	62.5	MA
8. Step ladder	9	56.25	MA
9. Water hoses	6	37.5	MA
10. Tint free cleaning	7	43.75	LA
11. Scrubbing foam	6	37.50	LA
12. Dish sponges	7	43.75	LA
13. Spray bottles	15	93.75	LA
14. Gloves	13	81.25	HA
15. Caution signs	3	18.75	HA
16. Mops squeezers	4	18.75	LA
17. White board	6	25	LA
18. White board marker	7	37.50	LA

19. White board eraser	9	43.75	LA
20. Linen for single bed	9	56.25	MA
21. Linen for double bed	12	56.25	MA
22. Glass ware	12	75	HA
23. Tea	12	75	HA
24. Coffee	12	71	HA
25. Sugar	12	75	HA
26. Powdered milk	12	75	HA
27. Bed single	3	18.75	LA
28. Bed queen	1	6.25	LA
29. Slippers	15	92.75	HA
30. Projector screen	5	31.25	LA
31. Overhead projector	2	31.25	LA
32. Electric fan	12	75	HA
33. First aid cabinet	10	62.50	MA
34. Instructor's chair	10	62.50	MA
35. Fire extinguisher	4	25	LA
36. Emergency signage	6	37.50	LA
37. Directional signage	3	18.75	LA
38. Air condition	0	0	O
39. Armed chairs	3	18.75	LA
40. Telephone	2	12.5	LA
41. Computer	5	31.25	LA
42. Television	3	18.75	LA
43. Refrigerator	2	12.5	LA
44. Hair dryer	3	18.25	LA
45. Alarm clock	3	18.25	LA
46. Coffee maker	2	12.25	LA
47. Electric kettle	5	31.25	LA
48. Electric jug	5	31.25	LA
49. Polisher	2	12.25	LA
50. Washers	2	12.25	LA
51. Flat iron	12	75	HA
52. Ironing board	6	37.50	LA
53. Drying/cleaning machine	3	18.25	LA
54. Cleaning detergent	12	75	HA
55. Liquid detergent	10	62.50	MA
56. Flashlight	8	50	MA
57. Light fritting	2	12.5	LA
58. Mirrors	12	75	HA
59. Wardrobes	3	18.75	LA
60. Hangers	12	75	HA
61. Ashtrays	15	93.75	HA

62. Strainers	10	62.50	MA
63. Spatula	10	62.50	N
64. Wooden spoon	10	62.50	LA
65. Piping bag	3	18.75	LA
66. Funnel	3	18.75	LA
76. Measuring spoon	4	25	LA
78. Tongs	3	18.25	LA
69. Measuring cup	3	18.75	LA
70. Ice cream scoop	11	18.75	MA
71. Can opener	13	61.11	HA
72. Kitchen scissors	10	81.25	MA
73. Peelers	10	62.80	MA
74. Pot	15	62.50	HA
75. Frying pan	15	93.75	HA
76. Casserole	15	93.75	HA
Total Average Mean	611	39.94	LA

It can be noted that the facilitates and equipment in terms of mops, brushes, gloves, caution sign, glassware, tea, coffee, sugar, powder, milk, slippers, electric fan, flat iron, cleaning detergent, mirrors, hangers, ashtrays, can opener, pot, frying pan, and casserole when needed by the learners in particular. It implied that there are the common and basic available facilities and equipment.

Considering the data there are many facilitates and equipment which are adequate like the following: Step ladder, Water hoses, Tint free cleaning, Scrubbing foam, Dish sponges, Spray bottles, Gloves, Caution, Linen for single bed double bed, glassware, tea, coffee, sugar, powdered milk, bed single, bed queen, slippers, projector screen, over head projector screen, overhead projector, electric fan, first aid cabinet, Instructor's chairs, telephone, computer, television, refrigerator, hair dyer, alarm clock, coffee maker, electric kettle, electric jug, polisher, washers, flat iron, ironing board, Dying/cleaning machine, light fritting, wardrobes, wooden spoon, piping bag, funnel, measuring spoon and tongs.

It means that there are facilities and equipment are more expensive in nature that need certain big amount of money to purchase them. Furthermore, they are not needed most of the time but still are important in nurturing the knowledge and skills of learners in Home Economics. It implied that these are significant teaching the area of Home Economics.

Considering the whole table, it could be synthesized that the facilities and equipment are less adequate proven by the overall average percentage of 3.94. It means that the Home Economics still deficient in facilities and equipment. It implied that the level of performance of the learners can be affected by the inadequately of the needed facilities and equipment.

Table 8 presents the correlation between school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the grade 10 TLE learners.

Table 8
Correlation between the School Facilities and Equipment and the Level of Performance of the Grade 10 TLE Learners

Variables	R	P-Value	Decision
School Facilities and Equipment and the Level of the Performance	.987	.028	Significant

The school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE Learners is significantly correlated. The computed P-valued is 028 which is lower than computed value of .987. The result is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significance correlation between the facilities, and the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners. It implied that the performance of the learners is affected by the school facilities and equipment.

Proposed Action Plan to Improve / Enhance the Level of Performance of the TLE Grade 10 Learners in Home Economics

Introduction

The proposed action plan has the purpose of improving the level of performance of the TLE Grade 10 learners in the area of Home Economics along: Cookery and Bread and Pastry Production. The action plan considered the profile of the teacher and the facilities and equipment to be correlated in the level of Performance of the TLE 10 learners in every quarter which is based from the record of the teachers.

The proposed plan of action has the following components in matrix form.

1. Areas of Concern
2. Targets / Objectives
3. Activities / Strategies
4. Persons / Agencies Involved
5. Time Frame
6. Budget
7. Success Indicator

The concrete frame of the proposed |Action Plan in found in the succeeding page.

Proposed Action Plan in Grade 10 TLE

Areas of Concern	Targets / Objectives	Activities / Strategies	Persons / Agencies Involved	Time Frame	Budget	Success Indicator
A. Profile of TLE 10 Teachers						
- Teacher Obligation	- Encourage TLE 10 Teacher to take NC and TM in their field of specialization.	- Provide the TLE 10 teachers training. - Link with TESDA for NC, TM training.	TLE 10 teachers, school principals, DepEd, TESDA.	Year round	P5,000 as needed	- 85 percent of TLE 10 teachers shall have attended NC and TM training and other related training.
B. Home Economics	- Encourage the teachers and learners to advocate and prioritize the acquisition and utilization and management of the facilities and equipment in Home Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TLE Teachers student, principal • Parent meeting • Presentation of the problem and issues in the inadequate facilities and equipment. • Procurement of facilities and equipment. • Management of the facilities and equipment's • Solicitation 	TLE 10 Teachers, School Principals, Learners, Parents, Alumni's	Year round as scheduled	As needed	- 80 percent of the teacher and learners shall have prioritize and advocate the acquisition, utilization, and maximize of facilities and equipment in Home Economics.
C. Level of Performance of Grade 10 TLE Learners						
1. Written Work	- Conduct assessment of the knowledge information acquired by the TLE 10 learners in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of data to be concerned • Gathering of date and information • Complete data and 	TLE Learners, School Principals, Learners DepEd	Year round	As needed	- 90 percent of the knowledge acquired based from the data and information

	their Home Economics	information must be ready and relevant				shall have been concerned properly.
2. Perform ance Tasks	- Ability to process and make some of information and concerned properly Done along Home Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities to be processed in the class • Identify their skills • Demonstration in front of the class • Presentation of work in accordance to relevance and appropriation. 	TLE 10 Learners and Teachers	Year Schedule or Monthly as scheduled	P20,000	- 85 percent of the learners shall have demonstrated strong ability to process and increases information in the areas of activities in the class.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations made from the analysis of the data.

Summary

This study sought to determine the level of performance of Grade 10 TLE learners in public secondary schools in the Municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan in relation to selected variables during the school year 2025-2026. Specifically, it intended to determine the following: level of adequacy of the facilities and equipment in TLE of public secondary schools along the area of Home Economics in terms of Written Work, Performance Tasks, and Quarterly Assessment, and the significance correlations between the profile and the level of performance, adequacy of the school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the learners.

The descriptive-correlational designs with a questionnaire was used. The respondents were 467 learners as subjects and of the study and 16 TLE 10 teachers who determined the level of adequacy of the facilities and equipment, and level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners. They were selected in total enumeration based from the record of the Public Secondary Schools in the Municipality of Bugallon, Pangasinan.

Findings

The salient findings of the study are as follows:

1. Majority of TLE Teachers are in the age bracket between 20 and 30, with BSE course without National Competency Certificate, Teacher I rank, and attended 3 to 4 times TLE training.
2. The Grade 10 TLE learners recorded a performance of fair in the 1st quarter, satisfactory in the 2nd quarter, very satisfactory in the 3rd quarter, and the 4th quarter in Home Economics along the 4 areas.
3. There is a significant correlation between the profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers and the performance of the TLE 10 learners.
4. The level of adequacy of facilities and equipment in Home Economics is less adequate.
5. There is significant correlation between the school facilities and equipment and the level of performance of the TLE Learners.
6. A plan of action to improve the level of performance of Grade 10 TLE learners can be formulated.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. The Grade 10 TLE teachers are young with basic educational qualifications, hold the lowest rank of teachers, and have very minimal specialized training in TLE.
2. The Grade 10 TLE learners have constantly improved to meet the expected level of performance in Home Economics and can perform the activities given them in Written Work, Performance Tasks, and Quarterly assessment.
3. The profile of the Grade 10 TLE teachers has influenced the level of the performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in Home Economics.
4. The facilities and equipment in Home Economics were not sufficient to meet the needs of the

learners use along the 2 areas.

5. The school facilities and equipment have affected the level of performance of the TLE 10 learners in Home Economics along the 2 areas.
6. A plan of action designed to improve the level of performance is formulated.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Procure TLE facilities and tools to enhance the teaching and learning process for the learners.
2. Teachers handling TLE subjects should undergo relevant training prescribe by the TESDA and acquire National Competency, Trainers Methodology (TM) and National Technical Vocational Trainers Competency (NTTC).
3. The proposed plan of action should be presented to the Schools Division I Superintendent for wider implementation in Pangasinan purposely to improve the level of performance of the Grade 10 TLE learners in Home Economics.
4. Similar research shall be conducted in other schools of Pangasinan I Division to improve the findings of the present study.

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